

Sharing Research Data with External Collaborators

During active research, data sharing with external collaborators is often necessary. [Switch](#) offers services for efficient data exchange, which support large file transfers and promote seamless collaboration. By leveraging these tools, researchers can maintain productivity and data integrity across institutional boundaries.

Important advice on sharing personal data

Be aware that sharing personal data requires specific solutions. In case you want to share personal data, contact IT-Services.

- Use encryption when sharing personal data; avoid unencrypted email, cloud services, or flash drives.
- Share personal data only with authorized collaborators.

Switch Filesender

Students and university staff can use the secure web application [Switch Filesender](#) to exchange large files with anyone:

- Maximum file size per upload: 300 GB
(multiple files can be uploaded simultaneously; the 300 GB limit applies to all files together)
- Maximum number of e-mail recipients: 50
- Maximum storage period for files: 60 days
- Supports data encryption with one click

Switch Drive cloud storage

[Switch Drive](#) enables collaborative work for students and university staff. Users can share individual files and folders for continuous collaboration. Switch Drive features include:

- 100 GB online storage per user
- Protected access
- Synchronized files and folders across multiple devices
- Access via [desktop client](#), [browser](#) or [mobile application](#)

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Switch Drive is usually bound to one person. If your project has a changing management, there is the possibility to get a [project folder](#), where larger amounts of data (up to 1 TB) can be shared. It can be requested from [IT-Services](#).

Servers are located in Switzerland, making Switch Drive a good alternative to many commercial cloud providers. However, Switch Drive is not a suitable storage location for unencrypted personal or other sensitive research data. Additionally, Switch Drive does not offer automatic backups, therefore users are responsible for backing up their own data.

